

Genomic Insights into *Staphylococcus aureus*: Mechanisms of Antibiotic Resistance and Virulence Gene Expression

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Abstract

Staphylococcus aureus is a major human pathogen responsible for a wide range of infections, from mild skin conditions to severe systemic diseases. The increasing prevalence of antibiotic-resistant strains, such as methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), poses significant challenges to global healthcare systems. This review provides a comprehensive analysis of the genomic mechanisms underpinning antibiotic resistance and virulence in *S. aureus*. Key resistance mechanisms include the acquisition of resistance genes through horizontal gene transfer, mutations in target sites, and the overexpression of efflux pumps. Additionally, the regulation of virulence factors, such as toxins, adhesion molecules, and enzymes, is controlled by complex genetic networks, including quorum sensing and global regulators like the agr and sar systems. Advances in whole-genome sequencing have facilitated a deeper understanding of the genetic diversity and adaptability of *S. aureus*. These insights are essential for developing innovative therapeutic strategies and mitigating the impact of this pathogen on public health.

Keywords: *Staphylococcus aureus*, Antibiotic resistance, Virulence factors, Genomic mechanisms, Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), Whole-genome sequencing.

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Introduction to *Staphylococcus Aureus*

Staphylococcus aureus also produces many adhesins or invasins, such as fibronectin/fibrinogen binding proteins and collagen adhesins, which are critical in the initiation of infections. Moreover, not only is the expression of these virulence factors coordinated by cell density through various regulatory systems, but much of the cell density-dependent gene expression occurs at the post-translational level (Samia et al., 2022; Tsouklidis et al., 2020).

Initially, in the 1940s and 1950s, extracellular products generated by strain 52A were examined for their ability to protect animals against challenges with the highly toxic staphylococcal extracellular products, such as α -toxin, a heat-stable nuclease, and enterotoxins associated with food poisoning. Protective extracellular proteins that had the capacity to protect animals against lethal challenges were partially

characterized. Subsequently, strain Smith 5R, shown to be less variable in the production of exoproteins, was used for DNA sequencing and structural and functional genomics analyses. Now, *S. aureus* isolates extracted over a 45-year period from a variety of human and animal hosts have been used to explore staphylococcal diversity and to determine the impact of horizontal transportation and genomic rearrangements triggered by bacteriophages on bacterial genome content. To this end, the nucleotide sequences of six different *S. aureus* isolates have been determined, enabling comparisons of strain variation/populations, surgical and asymptomatic infections, and nasal colonization. This review explores the genomics of *S. aureus* in relation to its antibiotic resistance and virulence gene expression (Sevin et al., 2021;Assefa & Amare., 2022).

Overview of Staphylococcus Aureus as a Pathogen

Staphylococcus aureus is a bacterial pathogen found ubiquitously in the human population, in hospital environments, and in the community. In addition, *S. aureus* is a zoonotic pathogen capable of infecting multiple animal species. The clinical spectrum of *S. aureus* diseases includes skin and soft tissue infections, invasive infections, toxic shock syndrome, pneumonia, and several other clinical entities. The organism is of great significance due to its ability to cause a variety of common infections and because of its potential to produce high mortality disease, especially given the development of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* strains (Howden et al., 2023; Matuszewska et al., 2020).

Staphylococcus aureus can survive in multiple ecological sites in the human host, and it has developed multiple means to escape from the host immune defenses. The last two decades have seen extensive efforts to sequence *S. aureus* genomes and to compare them by genomic and transcriptomic methods in both humans and animal hosts to generate a comprehensive map of *S. aureus* genes turned on during actual infections compared to growth in standard medium. This information is required to understand how the immune system recognizes *S. aureus* as well as how the pathogen modulates the host immune and other defense systems and thus causes disease (Abdullahi et al., 2021;Badawy et al., 2022).

Historical Perspective and Significance

The Oxacillin Resistant *Staphylococcus* (ORS) Group: Discovery of the *bla_K* gene and Amplification of β -lactam resistance. While penicillins and cephalosporins expanded the clinician's "armamentarium" against Gram-positive pathogens, the advent of methicillin and the host of broadly active semisynthetic penicillins provided particularly useful options for clinical use. As a result of unprecedented clinical success, the use of semisynthetic penicillins in hospitals mushroomed. This accelerated use, in turn, led to the prompt appearance of strains of staphylococci with resistance to these drugs. During a short period, the staphylococcal strains usually resistant to the glycopeptide antibiotics developed resistance to semisynthetic penicillins of methicillin type (Larsen et al., 2022 ;Ahmad et al., 2021).

This emergence led to a distinct survival advantage and prevalence of these penicillin-resistant staphylococcus lines, and halting the spread of these strains became a major concern for international public health. These strains received a number of different names in Denmark and England; in the USA and Australia; and a similar and well-known name that became finally established and recognized worldwide (Uddin et al., 2021).

Genomic Structure of Staphylococcus Aureus

Staphylococcus aureus, a spherical bacterium, has a small genome size (2.8 Mb) with a low percentage of G + C (approximately 33.6%). Phylogenetic studies grouped *S. aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* in one clade, indicating that these are close cousins that began their role as staphylococci with the evolution of the host vertebrates. The staphylococcal chromosome is relatively well conserved within the same species in comparison with genomes classified in the same genus. Despite this, a considerable

number of mobile genetic elements, including plasmids, phages, insertions, and transposons, have been identified in *S. aureus* genomes. Consequently, the *S. aureus* pan-genome is relatively large due to the existence of core clusters and variable gene clusters (Young et al., 2021; Al-Trad et al., 2023).

The differentiation of the genomes could have a fundamental role in the plasticity of the *S. aureus* pan-genome by generating copy numbers of swappable genome components. The structural analysis of coding regions has identified most of the gene targets that are important for the genetic features correlated to selective pressures, such as pathogenesis, host adaptation, and drug resistance. The distribution of functions within species of the staphylococcal pan-genome follows Little's Law, which defines optimal growth under conditions of dynamic environmental change. The loss and acquisition of new genes are relevant biological phenomena for a pathogen and vital for its evolutionary development, population structure, and pathogenic potential. The presence of a large fraction of nonessential genes contributed to such adaptive strategies, which increased genetic variability. The variability, which is also a distinctive characteristic of *S. epidermidis*, could be used as a hostage by the strategies of new chemotherapies (Kathirvel et al., 2021; Guan et al., 2024).

Chromosome and Plasmids

Staphylococcus aureus genome sequence analysis identified a circular chromosome with an average size of 2,821,361 bp and an average GC content of 32.8% to 32.9%. It is the largest bacterial genome carrying numerous virulence determinants for its pathogenesis mechanisms. Among the various *S. aureus* strains, these genes are carried in the mobile pathogenicity islands, also known as staphylococcal chromosome cassettes. The *S. aureus* chromosome consists of the core regions for conserved gene STSaSA, extended genes STSeSa, and non-core STSaSa regions. STSaSA regions are identified in all *S. aureus* strains as their core components, while other regions are associated with specific pathogenic functions. The genomic comparison of NCTC8325 and Mu50 demonstrated that the *S. aureus* Mu50 chromosome is larger by 180 kb. *S. aureus* structure-disrupting chromosomal lesions of a large inversion, translocation, and mobile pathogenic islands are present in Mu50 but not in NCTC8325 (Wisal et al., 2023; Seah et al., 2023).

In complete genome sequence analysis, *S. aureus* carries four or five plasmids simultaneously. They share high contents at the nucleotide sequences ranging from 98.9% to 100%, except for SaPIbov, which has 97.6% sequence identity. The 36.7 kb plasmid pSa consists of a core sequence of 15,428 bp, present in all five plasmids, consisting of a putative replication region, a multiple-AT-rich region, and the CC region. The AT-rich region is the major site for insertions, including a beta-lactamase, *ccrC*, and an additional copy of the *ccrC* gene. The average number of insertion elements in pSa carries more copies of insertion elements and has also been identified. Few genes carried on the pSa, and only pSa is shown to carry virulence genes, such as the toxic shock syndrome toxin 1, a transposon Tn916, and the staphylococcal complement inhibitor (Seah et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2021).

Mobile Genetic Elements

Originally, it has been described that MGEs could carry not only ARGs but also VGSs. This was no surprise as the term 'mobile genetic elements' had been adopted in order to emphasize the ability of such elements to jump from site to site within the DNA molecules of their hosts, thanks to genetic recombination, transposition, conjugation, DNA transduction, and various types of horizontal gene transfer. Following the discovery that a single bacterial cell commonly carries more than 5 MGEs, it was also shown that many *S. aureus* multi-resistant clones can be destroyed by leaving them their native chromosome but not the coding plasmids. This suggested that the presence of ARGs in plasmids cannot be sufficient to drastically change an antibiotic-susceptible *S. aureus* to drug-resistant. Other assumptions cannot be valid, such as the transfer of MGEs among bacterial cells of many other species of staphylococci other than *S. aureus* being simpler than predicted (Zhang et al., 2020; Li et al., 2024).

For example, reports indicate that a composite transposon of type Tn5406 can carry the ARG bla_Z; however, Tn5406 has never been found in *S. aureus*. In fact, it seems that *S. aureus* might be protected against the entry of the above element into its population by the particular average frequency of transposition of the Tn5406 gene. In other words, the movement of an ARG into different species of bacteria is dominated by the relative rate at which these bacteria accept MGEs, while the integration of the ARG into their own chromosome occurs more rarely (Makowska-Zawierucha et al., 2024; Sidhu et al., 2020).

Mechanisms of Antibiotic Resistance in Staphylococcus Aureus

Staphylococcus aureus is a major human pathogen that causes a wide variety of diseases. Successful management of these infections is complicated by the acquisition of antibiotic resistance genes. *S. aureus* has been prevalent in hospitals for years. The relative ease of transmission of *S. aureus* among people has led to the increasing importance of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* in community-onset infections. Many community-onset MRSA infections are skin and soft tissue infections, but more severe community-onset MRSA infections also occur. These infections are associated with the carriage of *S. aureus* in the anterior nares as well as increased levels of certain virulence factors (Mlynarczyk-Bonikowska et al., 2022; Li & Wang., 2021).

The rise of MRSA isolates with increased resistance to vancomycin is of particular concern. Vancomycin is the workhorse among antibiotics for severe MRSA infections; without it, only a few viable options for the treatment of these infections remain. The vast majority of MRSA variants that are more resistant to vancomycin have the genetic changes needed for increased vancomycin resistance in the absence of antibiotic pressure. These genetic alterations decouple the expression of resistant biopolymers from the regulatory signals generated by the presence of antibiotics and thus confer fitness costs. The genetic flexibility of *S. aureus* also produces strains that have only low intrinsic levels of antibiotic resistance, yet are able to acquire additional resistance by horizontal gene transfer from more resistant relatives of their commensal variants. *Staphylococcus aureus* uses plasmids and genomic islands to disseminate antibiotic resistance genes. While isolates from different clonal complex variants of *S. aureus* may carry related resistance genes, the genomic context of those genes often varies, leading to differences in their effect on antibiotic resistance levels. The fact that these genes are often not maximally expressed until the *S. aureus* isolates are under the selective pressure of antibiotics complicates the molecular detection of these antibiotic resistance genes. Sodium chloride exposure, daptomycin use, and glucose do not impact resistance nuclease activity, and therefore treatment with these resistances is not likely to be synergistic with the lysis provided by lysostaphin (Rivard et al., 2020; Mukherjee et al., 2021).

Beta-lactam Resistance Mechanisms

Staphylococcus aureus is quite successful at causing a plethora of human infections, ranging from mild infections such as washerwoman's dermatitis to invasive infections such as osteomyelitis or sepsis. Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) is a variant of *S. aureus* that displays resistance to most beta-lactam antibiotics including methicillin, nafcillin, and oxacillin. *S. aureus* resistance to these antibiotics relies on the *mecA* gene. *MecA* codes for a PBP2a protein that contains a penicillin-binding domain with low affinity for beta-lactam antibiotics. PBP2a can continue to catalyze new peptidoglycan synthesis within MRSA bacteria, while the other PBPs within the same microorganism are inactivated. To produce this resistant phenotype, *mecA* has to be located within the *S. aureus* chromosome or, more commonly in recent years, inserted in the chromosome when the microorganism acquires the Staphylococcal Chromosome Cassette *mec* (Mlynarczyk-Bonikowska et al., 2022; Taha et al., 2021).

It is worth noting that near the *mecA* genes in the SCC_{mec} there are the *mecR-1* and *mecI* genes. These regulators adjust *mecA* expression in response to the presence of a beta-lactam antibiotic by means of a

two-component signal transduction system. As a result, *mecA* is poorly expressed when a SCC*mec*-positive *Staphylococcus* strain does not find an antibiotic in the surrounding environment. However, the same gene can be highly expressed when bacteria find themselves in the presence of a beta-lactam antibiotic. Another gene, the *blaZ* gene, codes for a beta-lactamase that allows the hydrolysis of the beta-lactam antibiotic and its inactivation. It has been found in multiple *S. aureus* isolates that are not classified as MRSA. This gene confers resistance to *S. aureus* against benzylpenicillin and other members of the penicillin antibiotic family (Boonsiri et al., 2020; Marciniak et al., 2024).

Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA)

Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) is a major human and veterinary pathogen that has developed resistance to virtually all β -lactam antibiotics, including methicillin, nafcillin, and oxacillin. MRSA has become the major cause of nosocomial, hospital-acquired infections and is responsible for an increasing number of community-associated diseases, especially the epidemic clonal type CA-MRSA. MRSA is of grave concern due to its extraordinary ability to develop resistance to multiple antibiotics. Traditionally, MRSA has been classified into two distinct classes typified by the production of either a superantigen, typical of community-acquired CA-MRSA that is also MSSA, or by being metabolically inactive, having reduced growth, producing a clumping factor that confers protection against the phagocytic action of leukocytes, mounting acid tolerance, and being resistant to several antibiotics, rather typical of blood culture-positive nosocomial MRSA (Algammal et al., 2020 ;Belhout et al., 2022).

Optimum therapy for MRSA infections has been limited by the organism's ability to develop resistance to new antibiotics, a problem that has intensified due to the slow development of antibiotics active against MRSA. Current therapies for MRSA include vancomycin, linezolid, and quinupristin-dalfopristin, but the increasing prevalence of resistant strains has threatened the utility of each of these antibiotics. Recently, infections caused by MRSA strains containing novel resistance and killing factors have been associated with significant morbidity and mortality. *S. aureus* exhibits inducible and constitutive resistance to methicillin. The former is responsible for most of the infections and is characterized by in vitro susceptibility to methicillin, though most organisms contain a mutated penicillin-binding protein (PBP) 2 that has low affinity for β -lactam antibiotics and impairs the ability of such drugs to inhibit transpeptidation. The in vivo binding of methicillin to the MRSA PBP2 should cause cell lysis via one of three mechanisms: protein aggregation, defective division septum, or interrupted cell wall synthesis. The latter is typical of blood culture-positive nosocomial MRSA that are not only penicillin-binding protein-deficient but are also devoid of *mec*; its production will be activated by catabolite repression. The life-threatening condition antiphagocytosis is coded by the *asr* gene but protects cells from oxidants generated by the phagocyte's mineral-generating NADPH oxidase (Belhout et al., 2022; Pal et al., 2020; Crespo-Piazuelo & Lawlor., 2021).

Several transcriptional factors are associated with the MRSA phenotype, such as Δ *agrA*, *ctsR*, and *sarZ*. The opposite regulation by *CtsR* needs to be investigated further; complementation studies should be performed in various mutant backgrounds and with a variety of independent clones to demonstrate the mechanism of *CtsR*-dependent gene regulation. The ACME genome region is present only in MRSA strains and is alleged to be a marker for CA-MRSA. However, other recent reports show that the accession of the ACME region is a conserved trait in a family of related *S. aureus* strains. An additional non-mobile PBP2 mutant involved in the resistance to methicillin is PBP2A causing SCC*mec* V. Infection by hospital-associated MRSA results in increased mortality, excess intensive care unit stay, and extra hospital charges (Crespo-Piazuelo & Lawlor., 2021; Glajzner et al., 2023).

Virulence Factors in Staphylococcus Aureus

Staphylococcus aureus is a Gram-positive commensal of the human nares and skin, with additional carriage sites in humans and mammals, including companion animals, livestock, and domesticated animals, including horses. As a major human pathogen, *S. aureus* causes mild to severe infections, from skin lesions to invasive endovascular disease, pulmonary infections, food poisoning, and toxic shock syndrome. Over the years, scientific research has revealed that *S. aureus* possesses an enormous potential to express virulence factors, which are used as mechanisms to dysregulate the host immune response and to thrive and accumulate in various host cell types. Staphylococcus aureus is a common commensal of humans and an opportunistic pathogen. Although colonization with *S. aureus* is asymptomatic up to 50% of the time, *S. aureus* infections range in morbidity from mild to severe infections, including skin and wound infections, pneumonia, and endovascular disease. Skin infections, such as boils and folliculitis, are the most common types of *S. aureus* infections. Because carriage is a risk factor for infections caused by these bacteria, many studies have focused on identifying potential virulence factors that could contribute to the success of colonization (Cheung et al., 2021; Vlaeminck et al., 2020; França et al., 2021; Ali et al., 2019).

Toxins and Superantigens

Extensive study has gone into elucidating the mode of action and underlying mechanisms of these toxins. The action of any given toxin has wide-reaching effects on the cells involved, but a common underlying theme is the ability to induce the release of cytokines. There are some known receptors such as MHC II and CD28 to which these superantigens are able to bind. The structure of the superantigen/toxin and MHC II complex has been suggested through X-ray crystallography. This leads to a buildup of activated T-cells that can overproduce so-called pro-inflammatory cytokines, resulting in a dysregulation of the host immune response. Despite this, the majority of *S. aureus* infections do not result in toxic shock. Both skin and soft tissue infections and bacteremia-associated strains regularly harbor these genes, indicating a more complex interplay between colonizing and transient *S. aureus* strains and the host (Cheung et al., 2021; Howden et al., 2023; Bennett & Thomsen., 2020; Cheung et al., 2021).

The key question is in which environment these toxins are produced by the microorganism. They are members of the accessory gene regulator regulon. This gene allows for group behavior by encoding an autoregulatory mechanism of the RNAIII effector molecule, which controls the agr-dependent response genes. It is a quorum sensing-based system and is active in the post-exponential growth phase. There are additional regulators modulating toxin expression, such as the staphylococcal accessory regulator, saeRS, and the repressor proteins Rot and SarU, which enhance agr expression. While conditions such as oxygen levels, sulfur or glutamine starvation, and subdominant factors such as pH can all affect toxin production, there is considerable variation in the presence of these toxin genes in human population-associated lineages, and it is hypothesized that specific strains are selected for over others (Howden et al., 2023; Pidwill et al., 2021).

Adhesion Molecules and Biofilm Formation

Adhesion is the first step in the process of bacterial biofilm formation. The initial bacterial adhesion is mainly mediated by adhesion factors in Staphylococcus aureus, including teichoic acids and wall-associated proteins, such as fibronectin binding proteins, clumping factors, coagulase, and protein A. There are diverse molecular mechanisms and corresponding host cell receptors underlying *S. aureus* adhesion and invasion. Fibronectin-binding proteins and clumping factors A and B play important roles in interacting with host cell receptors to promote adhesion. Other proteins, including bone sialoprotein-binding proteins A and B and elastin-binding proteins, contribute to the adherence and colonization capacity of *S. aureus*. Protein A in *S. aureus* is an important cell wall-anchored adhesion molecule that

can bind to the fragment crystallizable region of the host immunoglobulin G (Wang et al., 2020; Zou et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2020; Kreve & Dos Reis., 2021).

Regulation of Virulence Gene Expression

The genetic basis of *S. aureus* is complex, involving a large repertoire of virulence factors that facilitate colonization, help the bacterium to evade host immune defenses, and permit the establishment of infection in a tissue-specific fashion. The expression of these factors is tightly regulated, responding to environmental signals and to physiological conditions. As a result, these virulence factors are expressed at different stages of the infectious process, and not all of them are expressed in equal amounts at any given time. This tight regulation ensures that the microbe coordinates defensive factors with attack strategies, conserves energy, and may reduce the generation of an overwhelming host immune response (Qin et al., 2022; Jurado-Martín et al., 2021).

In this chapter, we describe what is known about the environmental signals, the regulatory factors, the networks, and the mechanisms by which *S. aureus* gene expression is controlled. At the center of this regulation is a series of small "environmental signals" such as bacterial quorum-sensing peptides, and inhibitors of quorum sensing, and host-based signals such as heme, Mg²⁺, the level of CO₂, and the pH of the environment. The most well-characterized of these is the agr quorum-sensing system. This system does not stand alone and operates as part of a larger gene regulatory network that also includes many other regulatory factors. Some regulators govern the expression of single or a small number of similar target genes, whereas others are pleiotropic and can control the expression of multiple virulence genes, and even global processes such as the metabolic transition from anaerobic to aerobic respiration. It is the two small RNA molecules produced as part of the agr genetic cassette, Coa and RNAIII, that are the important mediators of the quorum-sensing communication system. Let us meet the friends of "agr." (Jurado-Martín et al., 2021; Pontes et al., 2020; Liao et al., 2022).

Quorum Sensing Systems

Positions in the agr locus of *Staphylococcus aureus* are ordered: agrA, agrC, agrB, agrD, agrC, agrA. AgrD is the precursor of Auto Inducer Peptide (AIP). The export of AgrD is a bit different. Due to the formation of an intermolecular disulfide bridge within AgrB, AgrD is modified into a tri-lactone. AgrD is then cleaved and exported out of the cell by AIP and AgrC. AIP will be detected by AgrC right after cell density reaches the critical level. The ligation of AIP will cause AgrC to phosphorylate and then activate the transcription of an RNA III molecule. The transcription of the RNA III molecule can be used as a marker to differentiate between group I and group II agr pheromones. Group I agr pheromones transcription is significantly upregulated when agrA or agrC are in the inactive form. The reverse applies to the group II agr pheromones. Mutagenesis experiments prove that the expression of the virulence gene is significantly affected by the agr locus (Derakhshan et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2021).

The bacterial cells use "Quorum Sensing" as a signal transduction system to sense the population. The AIP is rectangular; its chemical structure is different in each *Staphylococcus aureus* strain. The chemical structure of group IA AIP and group IC AIP is the same, due to the change of their fourth amino group from positively charged lysine to negatively charged glutamic acid. This change is enough to make these two AIPs recognized by different AgrC. The AgrC within the same species will not be activated by the AIP used by other species, so cross signaling wouldn't happen. The group III AIP has two types: one can only be recognized by rooster AgrC; the other one binds only to AgrC expressed on specific atopic human skin. The formation of a specific AIP ligand structure is the novel drug design. The cell density is very high, and the critical level of AIP is up to 500 fM; the fast increase of AIP influences the virulence gene expression. The overexpression of the agr gene has an immunosuppressive influence; this will promote the formation of chronic inflammation. Stopping the function of the agr locus and the molecules

used in the recognition of AIP is an alternative way rather than injecting anti-inflammatory drugs to treat the exudate (Derakhshan et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2020).

Two-Component Signal Transduction Systems

In the cell, one of the main mechanisms bacteria use to sense environmental conditions and react to stimuli is the use of two-component signal transduction systems. These systems themselves are usually composed of two proteins, and the pathways are some of the first to be involved in environmental signal sensing for the expression of genes that can help the bacteria overcome environmental stress. has 16 two-component signal transduction systems, of which several of the responses mediated by members of these pathways are not known (Wu et al., 2020; Rapun-Araiz et al., 2020).

The walkR response in particular is the most widely studied in . This response mediates the rapid reprogramming of the vegetative cell into a dormant, non-replicating small colony variant (SCV). A well-documented stress that induces this response in is exposure to a cell wall-active antibiotic, such as or . Other similar response pathways in involve the two-component responses mediated by saeRS, srrAB, and arlSR. In addition, the genes from the response mediated by the walkR that have been shown to be induced in conditions of exposure to such antibiotics, as well as in a condition where the metabolism of the cell is impaired, also encompass the genes that encode the two-component signal transduction pathways themselves (Qiu et al., 2021; Sharkey et al., 2023).

Genomic Technologies for Studying Staphylococcus Aureus

Staphylococcus aureus is a versatile bacterium and an etiological agent of numerous infectious diseases. Its genome is an inexhaustible source for numerous genomic, transcriptomic, and functional genomics studies. Genome sequencing is an essential component of each genomic research conducted in S. aureus. There are two distinct categories of genome sequences: (1) genomes derived from clinical isolates and (2) those generated in laboratory conditions. Together with genome sequences, high-throughput analysis methods and an increasing number of biological databases have made S. aureus a model organism to study various genomic questions. This review outlines the genomic tools and technologies that are commonly used in research studies conducted in S. aureus and precisely describes how they contribute to the understanding of antibiotic resistance and virulence gene expression in this important human pathogen (Schouls et al., 2022; Shinohara et al., 2023).

The release of the first genome sequence of Staphylococcus aureus is considered to be a significant milestone in microbiology, as it was the first sequence of the genome of a clinical bacterial isolate. The first completely sequenced S. aureus genome was from a methicillin-resistant strain. Since the first release, numerous S. aureus genome sequences have been published. The sequenced genomes cover a wide range of clonal complexes prevalent in different geographical regions. The availability of S. aureus sequencing products has opened new research possibilities that add to a better understanding of staphylococcal biology and virulence determinants and the molecular underpinnings of bacterial pathogenesis. In this review, we will provide an overview of the genomic techniques developed to respond to challenges that have arisen in S. aureus research. With constantly advancing technological breakthroughs, generating such records has become less expensive. Due to the low cost, high throughput, and increasing flexibility of the studies done, extensive utilization of genomic techniques can provide a much earlier resolution of the staphylococcal cell, both from a genetic and functional point of view. With this in mind, we will illustrate the potential value in using sequencing information to support the study of mechanisms of bacterial pathogenesis. We focus primarily, but not exclusively, on genome sequencing in reviewing acclaimed technologies. Discussions on high-throughput bacteriological approaches will also be touched upon (Shinohara et al., 2023 ; Yu et al., 2021; White et al., 2024).

Whole Genome Sequencing

Whole genome sequencing (WGS) has been widely employed to study variant profile evolution, characterize vertical and horizontal gene transfer dynamics of interest genes or mobile gene clusters, identify novel or rare functional genes and traits, as well as explain the experimentally acquired phenotypic changes. In the *S. aureus* field, a rapid identification protocol of gene transfer events has also been reported based on input plasmids, chromosomal, and output plasmid states. In a typical WGS experiment, the genomic DNA of an isolated strain is first sheared and used to build DNA libraries, followed by high-throughput sequencing. After cleaning the raw sequence data, the short sequence files are then assembled by referring to a related reference genome or de novo assembly (Bezerra et al., 2021; Oude et al., 2021).

In the end, explicit genomic features, including variant loci, SNPs, insertions, deletions, and recombination sites can be inferred and screened to proceed with further biological experiments. WGS also has a greater advantage over traditional PCR and amplicon sequencing in terms of scale, especially when large numbers of strains come from different isolates or diverse species. Intuitive and popular graphic software, as well as emerging big data analytics, also allowed scientists to demonstrate differences in their own important datasets (Oude et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2021).

Transcriptomics and Proteomics

During growth within an infected host, *S. aureus* is subject to very strong selective pressures, necessitating specific expression of virulence factors and major adaptations to nutrient availability. In vitro transcriptome and proteome studies have long provided a useful oversaturation of candidate virulence proteins, but technological barriers once prohibited in vivo analysis. However, with advances in chromatin immunoprecipitation, RNA, and ChIP-RNA sequencing protocols, there has been a rapid increase in in vivo-derived transcriptome and protein occupancy datasets, providing unprecedented insight into pathogen gene regulation during bacterial pathogenesis. *S. aureus* transcription dictates, at the level of both primary and alternative sigma activity, the virulence-related state, but how this occurs at the microbial population and single-cell level and how this is controlled is less well characterized and is a key area of continued interest (Nicolas et al., 2022 ;Saleem et al., 2024).

The in vivo *S. aureus* transcriptome has been profiled during human and mouse infections in various organs. To date, the enhanced investigation of human conditions is warranted, particularly exploiting the rapid evolution in clinical sequencing and diagnostic platforms, which will be underpinned by the continued functional deciphering of these infected tissues. Despite these limitations, the results from these datasets suggest that *S. aureus* significantly remodels its transcriptome and proteome in response to the infection environment. The greatest concordance in the differentially expressed genes between the in vivo conditions is achieved when a paired in vitro growth medium is used for comparison. While this concordance is beneficial for supporting bacteriology research hypotheses, this approach ignores the highly variable levels of distinct growth substrates and oxygen availability at different in vivo locations (Palma et al., 2020; Chu et al.,2022).

Clinical Implications of Antibiotic Resistance and Virulence in Staphylococcus Aureus

The pathogen *Staphylococcus aureus* is effectively controlled by numerous drugs that function against widely varying targets. However, the bacterium has the ability to develop antibiotic resistance to all clinically used antimicrobials. The acquisition of pharmacogenetic resistance determinants can inactivate a limited number of the available chemotherapies or modify the targets for the majority of the drugs, rendering them much less effective and sometimes ineffective. The successful transfer of these

pharmacogenetic resistance determinants to human strains, producing a multi-drug resistant bacterium, as well as the capacity of *S. aureus* to colonize participants in the healthcare system and the general population, makes MDR *S. aureus* a serious threat, particularly in hospital settings. *S. aureus* is an invasive, immunomodulatory, and degradative pathogen that is frequently associated with sepsis, skin and tissue infections, pneumonia, and infective endocarditis (Ali & O.A. 2019; Mlynarczyk-Bonikowska et al., 2022; Mlynarczyk-Bonikowska et al., 2022; Abushaheen et al., 2020).

Treatment Challenges and Strategies

Staphylococcus aureus remains one of the most prevalent multidrug-resistant bacteria, which complicates the management of infections caused by this pathogen. A growing number of antibiotics to which *S. aureus* strains are resistant have prompted research to reveal molecular and genetic mechanisms underlying the resistance. *S. aureus* has evolved several major cutting-edge strategies to retain the fitness of oxidative stress resistance, the cell wall homeostasis capability, and the α -toxin production in the presence of antibiotics (Guo et al., 2020; Mukherjee et al., 2021).

The stress-responding pathways or genes that are essential for the host-pathogen interactions are among those important targets for the future design of new therapeutics. This review focuses on the mechanisms of methicillin resistance and virulence gene expression, with an emphasis on β -lactam resistance, the antioxidant response, peptidoglycan degrading enzymes, and cell lysis. The potential molecular targets to develop new strategies for combating infections caused by β -lactam-resistant strains or hypervirulent *S. aureus* are summarized (Mukherjee et al., 2021; Jernigan et al., 2020).

Epidemiology and Surveillance

Most epidemiological studies on *Staphylococcus aureus* to date have been achieved using strain typing techniques and have focused on differentiating isolate sources, detecting clones with unique epidemiological properties, and delineating strain dispersal in specific geographical regions. Most of these studies have focused on isolates from healthcare-associated infections since *S. aureus* has been a prime cause of morbidity and mortality in hospitalized patients, and nosocomial infections are associated with drug resistance and a higher frequency of mortality. The molecular typing methods that have been employed for this purpose have involved biotyping, serotyping, pulsed-field gel electrophoresis, multilocus sequence typing, and *spa* typing, among others. The agar-based biotyping and serotyping methods have low resolution and reproducibility and cannot be used to genetically differentiate isolates at the subspecies level. In contrast, PFGE, MLST, and *spa* typing have all been shown to exhibit great discriminatory power and high reproducibility, which is important for routine epidemiological surveillance and for studying the pathogen's population structure and its evolution, both at global and local scales. Despite the fact that research on the bacteria has been limited to being focused almost exclusively on healthcare-related infections, the pathogen has emerged as one of the most frequently isolated pathogens in community settings, with a variety of associations to more severe diseases being described in the last decades (Abbas et al., 2019; Campos et al., 2022 ; Pal et al., 2020).

Community- and hospital-onset infections used to be caused by distinct lineages of *S. aureus*, but during the last 20 years, a large collection of studies have reported the emergence of *S. aureus* lineages that have the ability to cause infections in both community and healthcare settings. These strains have acquired resistance to unique dermatological and ocular antibiotics and have emerged as a major cause of tuberculosis, with the incidence of disease globally raised in the last decades. The understanding of the epidemiology of *S. aureus* and the mechanisms that underlie the genetic expansion of these lineages is considered fundamental and requisite for the development of novel prevention and treatment strategies. Although the population dynamics of *S. aureus* and the mechanisms of *S. aureus* adaptation to different hosts and environments are not fully understood, a large number of scientific studies have been performed to ameliorate this point. The work of many groups around the world has contributed by using typing methods or by obtaining complete genome sequences of isolates associated with diseases of central

importance to public health in the last few decades (Rasheed & Hussein., 2021; Campos et al., 2022; Pal et al., 2020).

Future Directions in Staphylococcus Aureus Research

The study of staphylococcal virulence has often been conducted using animal models, tissue culture, and in vitro data. The possible role of phages specific for *S. aureus* in regulating these virulence factors and ultimately causing the greatly heightened expression observed in vitro could be investigated. It may be that the strains which carry and express these factors highly do so while in areas of high phage abundance and that expression is tied to the growth phase and expression of lytic-phase phage, which may be triggered by emerging from these areas of abundant *S. aureus* into regions of high concentrations of iron or other bacterial alarm factors. Investigating the regulatory systems that underpin both the expression of these alarming virulence genes as well as their translation may yield ideal positions for the stem of the expression cascade (Cheung et al., 2021; Mrochen et al., 2020).

Electrostatic repulsions between the growing polypeptide being synthesized and the negatively charged ribosome would occur as the primary amino acid sequences support the formation of secondary and tertiary structures destined to interact with other copies of the factor being synthesized to reinstate protein function and that of the iron-dependent bacteriophage, if present. As well as encoding factors involved in virulence, staphylococcal genomic analysis has provided insights valuable for the design and development of various medicinal products. In the future, uses of *S. aureus* sequencing data may involve in silico screens of the *S. aureus* population to indicate multiantibiotic-resistant clones or strains expressing multiple virulence factors before these have been involved in significantly expanding outbreaks. Furthermore, research into other staphylococcal diseases such as *S. aureus* toxic shock syndrome, mastitis, staphylococcal endocarditis, and staphylococcal gelatinase may benefit from the approaches taken and findings associated with these more commonly focused *S. aureus* diseases (Mrochen et al., 2020; Cheung et al., 2021; Zeng et al., 2020).

Emerging Therapeutic Targets

The emergence of multiresistant strains of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* has necessitated new approaches for the management of *S. aureus* infections. The global dissemination of hospital-acquired MRSA strains has emphasized the need for new therapeutic agents that are effective in inhibiting and killing both HA-MRSA and CA-MRSA strains. Targets for rapid diagnostic tests, drugs, or vaccines towards MRSA include virulence factors, quorum-sensing systems, cell-wall biosynthesis enzymes, and metabolism and folded protein help enzymes such as the chaperone DnaK (Abebe & Birhanu., 2023).

Targeting Quorum Sensing Members of the staphylococcal accessory regulator and sigB regulons, signal transduction components, and two-component regulatory systems act simultaneously and share a degree of redundancy to coordinately modulate a range of physiological responses like virulence gene expression in a positive or negative manner via quorum sensing. SarA genes have already been targeted using decoy RNA activated peptide inhibitor of AgrAC or using autoinducing peptides to up-regulate virulence gene expression and so may represent a new class of antimicrobials. Small molecules such as Savirin and desHapten antibodies have been developed to interfere in the staphylococcal quorum-sensing response system to prevent initiation of staphylococcal infections. Targeting of agr-specific conversion of invasive *S. aureus* strains from a pathogenic state to a state that is less or not at all invasive may reduce bacterial dissemination and disease severity and support the host immune response. Agr-defective *S. aureus* strains may be good candidates for vaccine strains, as they have been shown to protect against invasive infection. Agr-specific bacteriophages with or without other pathogen-specific agents may be used on infected wounds and wounds contaminated with *S. aureus* to inhibit or prevent wound infection (Gopikrishnan & Haryini., 2024; Douglas et al., 2023).

Precision Medicine Approaches

There are two precision medicine approaches, organism detection and drug resistance, that could have a big impact on how *Staphylococcus aureus* infections are treated. First, with the increase in infections in joints with *Staphylococcus aureus*, hospitals would benefit by having the capacity to quickly test for the presence of the organism in joint fluid. This technology would provide faster treatment times and better patient outcomes. Second, accurate drug panels are being developed for other common community-onset bacterial pathogens. This technology should be expanded to include more *Staphylococcus aureus* genes that drive decisions to treat with vancomycin or the novel beta-lactam cefazolin or other specific medications (Tjandra et al., 2022; Struelens et al., 2024; Struelens et al., 2024; Avershina et al., 2023).

Conclusion

Staphylococcus aureus remains a critical public health challenge due to its capacity to develop antibiotic resistance and produce diverse virulence factors. The genomic adaptability of this pathogen, driven by horizontal gene transfer, mutations, and regulatory networks, has enabled it to persist in various environments and evade therapeutic interventions. Understanding the genetic mechanisms behind resistance and virulence, particularly in strains like MRSA, is crucial for developing targeted treatments and effective infection control strategies. Advances in genomic technologies, such as whole-genome sequencing, have provided valuable insights into the evolution and adaptability of *S. aureus*, paving the way for precision medicine approaches. However, combating this pathogen requires a multifaceted effort, including enhanced surveillance, innovative therapeutic development, and better stewardship of existing antibiotics. By integrating genomic insights with clinical practices, the global healthcare community can work toward reducing the burden of *S. aureus* infections and improving patient outcomes.

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